

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AND TURNOVER INTENTIONS OF ESL TEACHERS IN THE PHILIPPINES: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This study used an explanatory sequential mixed methods approach to explore the mediation effect of psychological well-being on the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intention of English as a Second Language (ESL) teachers in the Philippines. The quantitative data were collected from a sample of teachers in the ESL companies in the Philippines using adapted five-point Likert scale survey questionnaires, subjected to content validity and reliability analysis. Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson Product-moment Correlation, and the Mediating Analysis were used for quantitative data analysis. Statistical analysis showed that the occupational stress and turnover intention of ESL teachers have a moderate status, and psychological well-being has a high status. While there was a significant relationship found between occupational stress and psychological well-being, and psychological well-being and turnover intentions. A positive and strong relationship was observed between occupational stress and turnover intentions. The analysis also indicated that psychological well-being partially mediates the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. In the qualitative phase, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with participants selected based on the quantitative findings. The qualitative data confirmed the quantitative results and highlighted the confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-

being to the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. The study identified connecting-confirmation as the nature of data integration.

Keywords: *Education, educational leadership, occupational stress, psychological well-being, turnover intentions, ESL teachers, explanatory sequential design, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Turnover intention, a critical concern in organizational studies, represents an employee's conscious and deliberate willingness to leave their current employment (Park & Min, 2020). Such intentions have been referred to as one's willingness to resign from the organization and seek out other alternative sources of employment (Rumpoko et al., 2022). Research globally has shown the teacher intention to turn over as a prevalent and chronic challenge and it has remained a continuous problem up to this point in time (Kamau et al., 2020). Further, Teacher turnover is a global issue, affecting both developed and developing countries (UNESCO, 2024).

Furthermore, in the United States, 84 percent of teachers from the public schools and 82 percent of teachers from the private schools in 2020–21 were planning to leave but decided to stay on as teachers at the same school in 2021–22 (Stayers et al., 2024). In the latest data, US educator turnover intentions are reported to be increasing, contributing to more than 1 million teachers leaving for different jobs (Thomas & Hammond, 2017). Likewise, in Japan, Nagasaki, 30.7 percent of private teachers had stated they were not interested in staying in their current positions in the next few years (Tayama et al., 2019), and in China, teachers' turnover intention in private schools increased to 41 percent (Yang et al., 2021). In fact, in China, with 10.57 million full-time teachers, Chinese ESL teachers have a high level of turnover intention that have a detrimental effect on students' learning. (Li et al., 2021).

In China, the teaching profession, especially in the field of English as a Second Language (ESL), is known to be a highly stressful occupation due to heavy workloads and considerable pressures (Li et al., 2021). These factors can contribute to high turnover intentions among ESL teachers, potentially jeopardizing the quality of language instruction and the education system as a whole (Aguirre & Faller, 2018). Additionally, in Sweden, the issue of teacher turnover has been a significant challenge in the education system, with researchers and policymakers seeking to understand the underlying factors that contribute to this phenomenon (Toropova et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, the Philippines, as with many countries around the world, is dealing with the growing concern of teacher turnover intentions, affecting the quality of education and the stability of the teaching force (Aguirre & Faller, 2018). In the study conducted by Sumipo (2020), the country is now experiencing the broader issue of teacher turnover intention in private elementary schools, noting that the country experiences a constant turnover of teachers, especially at the basic education level. In Baguio City, a study by

Fernandez and Batani (2021) identified a considerable number of individuals, which is 62 percent, as having considered exiting the teaching profession.

Also, in Davao Region, the study of De La Pena (2018) shows that even when teachers are satisfied with their work, they may still intend to leave. Additionally, in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte, the School heads identified key impacts of teacher turnover such as increased workload, disruption in teaching consistency, and financial strain (Solano, 2024). Thus, Torpey (2023) stated that the prevailing problem attracted too many teachers in private schools to transfer and teach at public schools. This leads to projections for teachers planning to leave the occupation.

Previous research has identified a positive correlation between occupational stress and turnover intention. In fact, Xu et al. (2017) established that occupational stress leads to teacher turnover intentions. They demonstrated that there is a positive relationship between teacher occupational stress and turnover intentions. The study of Klassen and Chiu (2011) investigated practicing and pre-service teachers and showed that higher job stress was associated with increased intentions to quit. Similarly, Han and Wang (2023) studied L2 teachers, finding that occupational stress predicts turnover intentions.

Moreover, the study of Zhou et al. (2024) emphasizes the importance of teacher psychological well-being and its link to turnover intentions. Similarly, Doan et al. (2023) conducted the 2023 State of the American Teacher survey, revealing that teachers with poor psychological well-being were likelier to consider leaving their jobs. Additionally, Nazari and Oghyanous (2021) explored the role of experience in Second language teachers' occupational stress, psychological well-being and turnover intentions. The study found a significant correlation between these factors, with a stronger relationship observed among novice teachers.

This study employs mediation analysis to examine the role of psychological well-being as an intervening variable. In the study conducted by Halim et al. (2025), who reported that psychological well-being (PWB) significantly mediated the relationship between self-efficacy, social support, and academic resilience. Also, in the study of Dong et al. (2025), who found that psychological well-being significantly mediated the relationship between trait coping styles and depression among college students. Psychological well-being serves as a mediator in this study because it provides a crucial explanatory link between occupational stress and turnover intentions, especially within the emotionally demanding context of ESL teaching in the Philippines.

Existing research on teacher turnover intention often examines broader national contexts or specific school districts, such as those in the US or China (Yang et al., 2021). However, this study will investigate turnover intentions in the Philippines. It will solely explore the mediating effect of psychological well-being on the relationship between occupational stress and the turnover intention of ESL teachers. Moreover, most studies being read utilized quantitative, descriptive-correlational, and some employed qualitative research design (UNESCO, 2024). Compared to the current study, it will use mixed methods research, particularly explanatory sequential design. Also, less has been done

among online Teachers, such as teachers teaching English as a Second Language in the Philippines (Cuenca & Angoya, 2019). Therefore, the present study will solely explore the mediating effect of psychological well-being on the relationship between occupational stress and the turnover intention of ESL teachers teaching English as a Second Language in the Philippines.

The findings of this research hold significant social value, offering the Board of Directors of Online Teaching a vital foundation to implement responsive and sustainable measures addressing the pressing issue of ESL teacher turnover. By illuminating the role of occupational stress and psychological well-being, this study not only informs institutional policy but also inspires a wave of future research in a critically underexplored domain. Ultimately, it paves the way for the development of targeted programs that promote teacher retention, professional fulfilment, and educational stability benefiting not just educators, but the broader learning communities they serve. This aligns with Sustainable Development Goal number 4 on quality education to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.

The findings of this study will be disseminated to various online education companies to support efforts in retaining ESL teachers and enhancing their psychological well-being. Beyond the corporate sphere, the results will be shared with academic leaders, institutional administrators, educators, researchers, and conference participants, extending to journal editors, publishers, peer reviewers, and conference organizers across local, national, and international colleges and universities. To ensure scholarly rigor and global reach, the study is intended for publication in a double-blind peer-reviewed international journal, contributing to the growing body of literature on teacher retention and psychological well-being in the digital education landscape

Research Questions

1. What is the status of occupational stress, psychological well-being, and turnover intentions of ESL teachers?
2. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 2.1 Occupational stress and psychological well-being?
 - 2.2 Psychological well-being and turnover intentions?
 - 2.3 Occupational stress and turnover intentions?
3. Does psychological well-being significantly mediate the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions?
4. What are the standpoints of the participants regarding the significant findings from the quantitative data?
5. How do the qualitative results explain the quantitative findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in the Philippines, specifically Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao since most Filipinos speak English, and it is one of the most English-speaking nations in the world. Over 14 million Filipinos are English speakers, which has been one of the official languages of the country for a long time. Most online teachers in the Philippines earn their income by teaching English. The researcher utilized a mixed methods approach specifically the explanatory sequential design. In this study of Saraswati & Devi, 2023 that mixed methods designs are relatively recent modes of investigation that social scientists frequently use. The core principle of mixed methods research lies in the strategic integration of qualitative and quantitative approaches throughout the research process. Additionally, this integration can manifest at various stages, including the design phase, data collection phase, data analysis phase, and interpretation phase (Palinkas et al., 2019). The rationale behind the use of mixed methods is often to achieve triangulation, completeness, or complementarity, where different methods are used to corroborate findings, explore different facets of a phenomenon, or expand the breadth and depth of understanding (Pluye & Hong, 2013). The researcher collected first the quantitative data using adapted survey questionnaires from previous similar studies with a five-point Likert Scale and statistically analyzed the results. Descriptive correlation approach was used to address the problems and multiple variables investigated noting that while correlations can help show a relationship, it does not indicate causation (Cherry, 2023). The correlated variables include occupational stress, psychological well-being and turnover intentions of ESL teachers in the Philippines.

In the quantitative phase, adapted questionnaires were utilized to gather responses from the participants regarding the variables investigated in this study. These questionnaires comprised the Occupational Stress Scale (OSS) designed by House et al. (1979) to quantify the frequency to which employees are bothered by stressful events; Psychological Well-being Questionnaire; adopted from Springer and Hauser (2006), which comprises a set of statements representing the six dimensions of psychological well-being: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance; and Turnover Intentions Questionnaire, adopted from the Expanded-Multidimensional turnover intentions: Scale development and validation Questionnaire of Ike et al., (2023), to quantify turnover intentions according to the planned behaviour theory model. The researcher used these questionnaires to respond to this study's primary aim, which was, assessing the mediating role of psychological well-being between occupational stress and ESL teachers' turnover intentions.

The first part of the questionnaire was the determination of the status of occupational stress, the second part was the determination of the status of psychological well-being, and the third part was the determination of the status of turnover intentions of the ESL teachers.

Occupational Stress Scale (OSS). The eleven components of occupational stress are HR (Human Relations), TM (Time Management), JI (Job Identity), JR (Job Relationships), OS (Organizational Support), SE (Stress Experience), CC (Classroom Control), JM (Job Motivation) SP (Students' Parents), ES (Emotional Stress), SHE (Students' Home Environment). Content validity assessment confirmed 36 items. The reliability of the questionnaire, 35 out of 36 items, was confirmed. The EFA calculation of the items showed that the measures could be classified into 11 factors, and the factor load of all items was above 0.3, being valid. In addition, the calculation of the second-order Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) showed that the 11 factors would explain the construct of occupational stress ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, the goodness-of-fit index results showed high fitness of the model.

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Occupational stress among teacher is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Occupational stress among teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Occupational stress among teacher is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Occupational stress among teacher is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Occupational stress among teacher is never manifested.

Psychological Well-being Questionnaire. The six components of psychological well-being include autonomy, environmental mastery, personal development, positive interpersonal relationships, life purpose, and self-acceptance are represented in a number of statements in this tool. Statements are rated by respondents on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 denotes strong disagreement and 5 denotes strong agreement. A high score for each category means that the respondent is an expert in that particular area of their life. On the other hand, a low score indicates that the respondent finds that specific concept difficult to understand. Self-acceptance ($\alpha=.93$), positive relationships with others ($\alpha=.91$), autonomy ($\alpha=.86$), environmental mastery ($\alpha=.90$), life purpose ($\alpha=.90$), and personal development ($\alpha=.87$) are the metrics used to measure internal consistency. The following ranges were used in the interpretation of data gathered in this survey, which underwent pilot testing to be fitted for Filipino teachers.

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The psychological well-being of teachers is always exhibited.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The psychological well-being of teachers is oftentimes exhibited.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The psychological well-being of teachers is sometimes exhibited.

1.80 – 2.59	Low	The psychological well-being of the teachers is seldom exhibited.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The psychological well-being of the teachers is not exhibited.

Turnover Intentions Questionnaire. Subjective social status, organizational culture, personal orientation, expectations, and career are the five different aspects of turnover intentions that are evaluated by the questionnaire. The EMTIS included 25 items, and the responses are based on a five-point Likert-type format, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 5 denoting "strongly agree." The following ranges were used in the interpretation of data that gathered in this survey:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Turnover intention of teachers is Always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Turnover intention of teacher is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Turnover intention of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Turnover intention of teacher is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Turnover intention of teachers is never observed.

An interview guide was utilized to gather data in the qualitative strand. The researcher prepared an interview guide. The questions were based on the data obtained in the quantitative phase and were composed of open-ended questions on the lived experiences of ESL teachers pertaining to psychological well-being, occupational stress, and their turnover intentions. To ensure its clarity, relevance, and appropriateness, the interview guide underwent a rigorous validation process by experts in qualitative research. The validated and tested interview guide ultimately supported the credibility and trustworthiness of the qualitative data gathered. The data were coming from low and high results, and were validated by the experts in the field. Their recommendations were reflected in the final guide.

In the thematic analysis, the main goals of the strategy were to find, evaluate, and record any patterns or themes in the data. Themes were recurring patterns across multiple data sets that were important for characterizing a phenomenon and were related to a specific research question. Before starting the thematic analysis, the researcher read the transcripts several times to become acquainted with the information. After that, the information was arranged to create initial codes. Ideas were broken down into smaller units of meaning through coding. The codes were then analyzed and categorized into themes. The emerging concepts were examined, refined, and developed (Creswell, 2017).

Lastly, the integration of the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data was carried out. The integration of qualitative and quantitative analysis, also known as mixed methods research, involved combining both numerical and descriptive data to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. This approach helped address the limitations of relying solely on one type of data by leveraging the strengths of both (Fetters et al., 2013).

RESULTS

Shown in this chapter are the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings. Specifically, this chapter reveals both quantitative and qualitative data relevant to address the research questions formulated in Chapter 1.

Status of Occupational Stress of ESL Teachers

It is reflected in table 1 that the overall mean of occupational stress of ESL teachers is 2.67 which is described as moderate. It means that the occupational stress among teachers is sometimes manifested. In addition, its minimal standard deviation of .75 shows that the responses of the teachers are clustered close to the mean.

Table 1
Status of Occupational Stress of ESL Teachers

		Mean	SD	Description
Human Relations				
1.	Having students who make their job stressful.	2.57	1.08	Low
2.	Feeling they cannot be themselves when they are interacting with their administrator.	2.49	1.11	Low
3.	Having disagreements with their fellow teachers are a problem for them.	2.25	1.18	Low
4.	Getting too little support from the teachers with whom they work.	2.34	1.18	Low
5.	Feeling their fellow teachers think they are not doing a good job.	2.25	1.11	Low
6.	Thinking badly of themselves for not meeting the demands of their job.	2.60	1.12	Moderate
7.	Being unable to express their stress to those placing demands on them.	2.57	1.17	Low
	Category Mean	2.44	.95	Low
Time Management				
1.	Having too much to do and not enough time to do it.	2.80	1.12	Moderate

2.	Having to take work at home to complete it.	2.69	1.17	Moderate
3.	Being unable to keep up with correcting papers and other schoolwork.	2.59	1.15	Low
4.	Having difficulty organizing their time to complete tasks.	2.66	1.11	Moderate
	Category Mean	2.68	1.01	Moderate

Job Identity

1.	Putting self-imposed demands on themselves to meet scheduled deadlines.	3.34	1.07	Moderate
2.	Teaching is stressful for them.	2.47	1.10	Low
3.	Experiencing frequently one or more of these symptoms: stomachaches, backaches, elevated blood pressure, as well as stiff necks and shoulders.	2.97	1.20	Moderate
4.	Finding their job tires them out.	2.57	1.15	Low
	Category Mean	2.84	.88	Moderate

Job Relationships

1.	Having students who lack the motivation to learn negatively affects the progress of students.	3.27	1.10	Moderate
2.	Having difficulty working relationship with their administrator (s).	2.42	1.05	Low
3.	Having an administrator who makes demands of them that they cannot meet.	2.36	1.08	Low
	Category Mean	2.68	.86	Moderate

Organizational Support

1.	Feeling of having administrator who does not approve the job they do.	2.30	1.08	Low
2.	Feeling isolated in their job and in confronting their problems.	2.35	1.15	Low
3.	Feeling powerless to solve their difficulties.	2.39	1.13	Low
	Category Mean	2.35	1.06	Low

Stress Experience

1.	Experiencing headaches.	3.30	1.28	Moderate
2.	Finding themselves complaining to others.	2.87	1.19	Moderate
3.	Being unable to use an effective method to manage their stress such as relaxation techniques, and others	2.83	1.09	Moderate
4.	Having stress management techniques would be useful in helping them cope with the demands of their job.*	2.39*	1.15	High
	Category Mean	2.85	.70	Moderate

Classroom Control

1.	Having difficulty in controlling their class.	2.39	1.10	Low
2.	Becoming impatient/angry when their students do not do what they ask them to do.	2.49	1.12	Low
	Category Mean	2.44	1.03	Low

Job Motivation

1.	Being tense by the end of the day.	2.44	1.16	Low
2.	Feeling depressed about my job.	2.32	1.13	Low
	Category Mean	2.38	1.08	Low

Students' Parents

1.	Having parents of their students as sources of concern for them.	2.97	1.14	Moderate
2.	Having parents' disinterest in their child performance at school concerns them.	3.18	1.14	Moderate
3.	Feeling their students' parents who think they are not doing a satisfactory job of teaching their children.	2.60	1.07	Moderate
	Category Mean	2.92	.94	Moderate

Emotional Stress

1.	Being frustrated and/or feel angry.	2.31	1.12	Low
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2.	Worrying about their job.	2.65	1.17	Moderate
	Category Mean	2.48	1.05	Low
Students' Home Environment				
1.	Having home environment of their students that concerns them.	3.32	1.14	Moderate
	Category Mean	3.32	1.14	Moderate
	Overall Mean	2.67	.75	Moderate

Note: Item with asterisk is recoded because it is a positive construct while the variable is a negative construct.

Status of Psychological Well-being of ESL Teachers

The status of psychological well-being reflected in table 2 has an overall mean of 3.57 described as high which means that the psychological well-being of teachers is oftentimes exhibited. In addition, its standard deviation of .37 which is less than one shows that the responses of the ESL teachers are clustered close to the mean.

Table 2
Status of Psychological Well-being of ESL Teachers

		Mean	SD	Description
Autonomy				
1.	Expressing out their opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people.	3.81	.88	High
2.	Believing that their decisions are usually influenced by what everyone else is doing.	3.85	.81	High
3.	Not worrying about what other people think of them.	3.32	1.15	Moderate
4.	Being not influenced by people with strong opinions.	3.54	1.09	High
5.	Having confidence in their opinions, even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	3.68	.85	High
6.	Believing that it is not difficult for them to express their own opinions on controversial matters.	3.10	.99	Moderate
7.	Judging themselves by what they think is important, not by the values of what others think is important.	3.80	.96	High

	Category Mean	3.59	.51	High
Environmental Mastery				
1.	Feeling they are in charge of the situation in which they live in general.	5.00	.00	Very High
2.	Having the demands of everyday life often get them down. *	3.00 *	.00	Moderate
3.	Not fitting in very well with the people and the community around them. *	3.00	.00	Moderate
4.	Being quite good at managing the many responsibilities of their daily life.	5.00	.00	Very High
5.	Feeling overwhelmed by their responsibilities*	1.00 *	.00	Very Low
6.	Having difficulty arranging their life in a way that is satisfying to them. *	1.00*	.00	Very Low
7.	Having been able to build a home and a lifestyle for themselves that is much to their liking.	5.00	.00	Very High
	Category Mean	3.29	.00	High
Personal Growth				
1.	Being not interested in activities that will expand their horizons. *	2.63*	1.17	Low
2.	Thinking it is important to have new experiences that challenge how they think about themselves and the world.	4.34	.83	Very High
3.	Having not really improved much as a person over the years when they think about it.*	3.00*	1.14	Moderate
4.	Having the sense that they have developed a lot as a person over time.	3.92	.89	High
5.	Not enjoying on being in new situations that require them to change their old familiar ways of doing things. *	2.77*	1.16	Moderate
6.	Having life as a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth.	4.54	.75	Very High
7.	Having given up in trying to make big improvements or changes in their life a long time ago.*	2.68*	1.22	Moderate
	Category Mean	3.67	.62	High
Positive Relation				
1.	Having most people see me as loving and affectionate.	4.08	.78	High
2.	Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for them. *	3.10*	1.19	Moderate

3.	Feeling lonely because they have few close friends with whom to share their concerns. *	3.20*	1.25	Moderate
4.	Enjoying personal and mutual conversations with family members or friends.	4.28	.85	Very High
5.	Experiencing people would describe them as a giving person, willing to share their time with others.	4.07	.78	High
6.	Not experiencing many warm and trusting relationships with others. *	3.20*	1.16	Moderate
7.	Knowing that they can trust their friends, and they know they can trust them.	3.97	.88	High
Category Mean		3.70	.58	High
Purpose in Life				
1.	Living life one day at a time and do not really think about the future. *	2.87*	1.13	Moderate
2.	Having a sense of direction and purpose in life.	4.07	.89	High
3.	Having their daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to them. *	3.40*	1.13	High
4.	Not having a good sense of what it is they are trying to accomplish in life. *	3.42*	1.14	High
5.	Having enjoyed making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	4.24	.90	Very High
6.	Being not one of those who are wandering aimlessly through life	3.50	1.12	High
7.	Feeling sometimes as if they have done all there is to do in life *	2.79*	1.07	Moderate
Category Mean		3.47	.52	High
Self-acceptance				
1.	When looking at the story of their life, they are pleased with how things have turned out.	3.97	.93	High
2.	In general, feeling confident and positive about themselves	4.06	.86	High
3.	Feeling like many of the people they know have gotten more out of life than they have.*	2.43*	.97	Low
4.	Liking most aspects of their personality.	3.90	.86	High
5.	Feeling disappointed about their achievements in life in many ways *	3.20*	1.16	Moderate
6.	Having attitude about themselves that is probably not as positive as most people feel about themselves. *	2.73*	1.05	Moderate
7.	Comparing themselves to friends and acquaintances makes them feel good about who they are *.	2.84*	1.19	Moderate
Category Mean		3.30	.55	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.57	.37	High

Note: Item with asterisk is recoded because it is a negative construct while the variable is a positive construct

Status of Turnover Intention of ESL Teachers

It is shown in Table 3 that the status of turnover intention of ESL teachers has an overall mean rating of 2.73 which is described as moderate. It means that the turnover intention of teachers are oftentimes observed. Considering the degrees of dispersion in this variable, the standard deviation is .81, indicating that the responses are clustered near the mean.

Table 3
Status of Turnover Intention of ESL Teachers Expectation.

	Mean	SD	Description
Subjective Social Status			
1. Not liking the image of them they see in the future if they remain in their organization	3.11	1.18	Moderate
2. Leaving them no choice in their present job but to look for an alternative job offer that will benefit their status.	2.95	1.16	Moderate
3. Feeling often like quitting their job because their present job position is not compatible with their job resume.	2.52	1.08	Low
4. Feeling like quitting their job because of their marital status	2.13	1.18	Low
Category Mean	2.68	.91	Moderate
Organizational Culture			
1. Feeling often like staying at home than going to work because of the way their organization is structured.	3.14	1.21	Moderate
2. Being seriously considering quitting this job because of the organizational practices and policies.	2.47	1.12	Low
3. Having major dissatisfaction in life comes from their job environment.	2.53	1.19	Low
Category Mean	2.72	.99	Moderate

Personal Orientation

1.	Leaving their present job is their ultimate priority now because of family demand.	2.47	1.22	Low
2.	Having family who is not happy with the nature of their job.	2.18	1.16	Low
3.	Considering leaving their job as a result of their health status.	2.42	1.21	Low
4.	Being fit enough to continue this job in the near future	2.35	1.14	Low
5.	Feeling like quitting their job because the organization does not keep to its promise.	2.39	1.12	Low
6.	Having most people whose opinions they respect think they should leave their job.	2.29	1.17	Low
7.	Intending to leave this organization in the next one year.	2.45	1.22	Low
8.	Feeling like quitting this organization because they see no future in it.	2.28	1.12	Low

Category Mean	2.36	.97	Low
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Expectation

1.	Having healthcare package which is so poor to compare to the kind of work they do.	2.80	1.10	Moderate
2.	Getting better offer, they will leave their present job because of job insecurity	2.93	1.21	Moderate
3.	Feeling often that their present job is not worth the offer.	2.62	1.11	Moderate
4.	Having preferred working where they will be respected and recognized regardless of the pay,	3.79	1.13	High
5.	Having not gotten an acceptable alternative offer/job that is lucrative as what has been holding them in their job.	2.92	1.20	Moderate

Category Mean	3.01	.85	Moderate
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Career Growth

1.	Often feeling like quitting from this organization because their years of service do not reflect their present job designation.	2.53	1.08	Low
2.	Wanting to learn few things concerning their job career in this organization and leave.	3.00	1.14	Moderate
3.	Knowing they deserve a better job, they will go for it when they find one	3.32	1.22	Moderate
4.	Needing a work environment that will improve them, they do not get it in their organization.	2.93	1.24	Moderate
5.	Feeling like quitting from their organization because it does not create opportunity for advancement and development.	2.71	1.15	Moderate
Category Mean		2.90	.97	Moderate
Overall Mean		2.73	.81	Moderate

Significance of the Relationship of Occupational Stress, Psychological Well-being and Turnover Intentions

The correlation of variables are presented in table 4 It shows that occupational stress has a strong negative relationship to psychological well-being of teachers ($r = -0.51$) with a p-value of 0.00 that is less than the alpha set at .05 (two-tailed) level of significance. The results provides enough support that the relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being is significant. Also, it means that as occupational stress of teachers decreases their psychological well-being increases.

Meanwhile, psychological well-being reveals a significant negative strong relationship with turnover intentions of teachers ($r = 0.58$) and a p-value of .00 which is less than the alpha set at .05 (two-tailed) level of significance. This results provides sufficient evidence that the relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intentions is significant. It means that as the level of psychological well-being decreases, their level of turnover intentions significantly increases.

Table 4

Significance of the Relationship of Occupational Stress, Psychological Well-being, and Turnover Intentions

Relationships of Variables	r	p-value	Remarks
Occupational Stress and Psychological Well-being	-0.51	.00	Significant
Psychological Well-being and Turnover Intentions	-0.58	.00	Significant
Occupational Stress and Turnover Intentions	.80	.00	Significant

Significance of the Mediating Effect of Psychological Well-being on the Relationship between Occupational Stress and Turnover Intentions

The mediating analysis was conducted using JASP applications. In Table 5, the direct effects, indirect effects, total effects, and path coefficients are presented. The direct effect of the independent variable, occupational stress on the dependent variable, turnover intentions without considering the mediator, psychological well-being is 0.901. It indicates that for each unit increase in the occupational stress, turnover intentions increase by 0.901 units directly. This means that there is a significant relationship between the occupational stress and the turnover intentions, but still need to consider the mediation process to see if the relationship is explained by psychological well-being.

Meanwhile, the indirect effect of occupational stress on turnover intentions through psychological well-being is 0.160. As such, occupational stress affects the mediator variable, psychological well-being, which then affects the dependent variable, turnover intentions. It means that part of the effect of occupational stress on turnover intentions happen through psychological well-being. This suggests that psychological well-being does play a role in explaining how the occupational stress impacts turnover intentions.

Standpoints of the Participants on the Salient Points in the Quantitative Results

Shown in Table 7 are the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding Occupational stress, Psychological well-being, and Turnover intention. The essential themes generated are as follows: confirmed moderate rating of occupational stress; confirmed high level of psychological well-being; and disconfirmed moderate level of turnover intention.

Table 7

Standpoints of the Participants on the Salient Points in the Quantitative Results

Level	Essential Themes	Typical Reasons
Occupational stress		Student-Related Challenges are manageable with Adaptation

	Confirmed moderate rating of occupational stress	Passion and professional commitment buffer stress Time management and dual teaching loads cause fatigue, but teachers adapt External technical issues are occasional, not persistent Stress lessens over time through experience and emotional regulation Stress is offset by positive student engagement
Psychological well-being	Confirmed high level of psychological well-being	Appreciation from students and parents enhances emotional fulfillment Witnessing student growth creates deep professional purpose Positive student engagement energizes and motivates teachers Student progress reinforces joy and career satisfaction Supportive and open learning environments cultivate positivity Student improvement inspires continuous professional growth
Turnover intention	Disconfirmed moderate level of turnover intention	Strong sense of commitment and professional growth Personal fulfillment and sense of calling acceptable work conditions and schedules Resilience amid technical or environmental challenges Positive student relationships and engagement Ongoing passion and enjoyment for teaching

Standpoints of the Participants on the Relationships between Occupational stress, Psychological well-being, and Turnover intention

Shown in Table 8 are the standpoints of the participants on the relationships between occupational stress, psychological well-being, and turnover intention. The essential themes generated are as follows: Confirmed strong negative relationship of occupational stress to the psychological well-being, disconfirmed significant negative strong relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention, confirmed positive and strong relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions.

Table 8

Standpoints of the Participants on the Salient Points in the Quantitative Results

Level	Essential Themes	Typical Reasons
Relationship of occupational stress to the psychological well-being	Confirmed strong negative relationship of occupational stress to the psychological well-being	Stress leads to emotional strain and anxiety
		Stress spills over into personal life
		Stress diminishes motivation and job satisfaction
		Stress reduces ability to enjoy teaching moments
		High pressure from deadlines and reporting triggers mental distress
		Stress hinders professional growth and learning
Relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention	Confirmed significant negative strong relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention	Improved stress management over time
		Stress is temporary and manageable
		Emotional resilience and mental framing
		Stress tolerance improves with experience
		Work environment becomes more bearable over time
Relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions	Confirmed positive and strong relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions	Initial stress doesn't translate to long-term resignation plans
		High workload and administrative pressure lead to burnout
		Increased stress triggers desire for career change
		Excessive stress makes job unsustainable
		Accumulated personal and work stress intensifies turnover intentions
		Persistent difficulties and situational stressors weaken commitment
		Stress leaves no other option but to quit
Psychological strain makes giving up more likely		

Standpoints of the Participants on the Mediating Effect of Psychological Well-being to the Relationship between Occupational Stress and Turnover Intentions

Shown in Table 9 are the standpoints of the participants on the mediating effect of psychological well-being to the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. The essential theme generated is the confirmed partial mediation of

psychological well-being on the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions.

Table 9

Standpoints of the Participants on the Mediating Effect of Coping Strategies on the Relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions

Level	Essential Themes	Typical Reasons
Mediation analysis	Confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-being to the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions	<p>A sense of support and being valued buffers stress</p> <p>Strong psychological well-being enables stress resilience</p> <p>Poor psychological health amplifies the impact of even minor stressors</p> <p>Psychological well-being is a critical resource in teaching</p> <p>Psychological depletion leads to burnout and exit</p> <p>Psychological strain makes giving up more likely</p>

Data Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

Illustrated in Table 10 is the joint display of quantitative and qualitative results. This contains the research area, quantitative and qualitative results, and the nature of integration. In the research area column are the status of the variables of the study, relationships among the variables, and mediation effect of the mediating variable towards the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable. The qualitative results column displays the participants' responses as core ideas from Tables 7, 8 and 9 which show confirmation to the quantitative results column. The nature of data integration column shows the type of mixing used in the study which revealed that the qualitative findings connect and confirm with the quantitative findings.

Table 10

Joint Display of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

Research Area	Quantitative Results	Qualitative Results	Nature of Integration
Occupational stress	The overall mean of occupational stress	Participants shared that	Connecting-student confirmation

	<p>among the respondents is 2.67, which is described as moderate. It means that the occupational stress among teachers is sometimes manifested.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 1)</p>	<p>challenges are manageable through adaptation. Passion and commitment help buffer stress. While dual teaching loads and time management cause fatigue, teachers learn to cope. Technical issues are occasional, and stress lessens with experience. Positive student engagement offsets stress, making the work fulfilling.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 7)</p>	
Psychological well-being	<p>The overall mean of Psychological well-being among the respondents is 3.57, described as high, which means that the psychological well-being of teachers is oftentimes exhibited.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 2)</p>	<p>Participants shared that appreciation and student growth enhance emotional fulfillment and purpose. Positive engagement and progress bring joy, motivation, and inspire continued professional growth.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 7)</p>	Connecting-confirmation
Turnover intention	<p>The overall mean of turnover intention among the respondents is 2.73, which is described as moderate. It means that the turnover intention of teachers is oftentimes observed.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 3)</p>	<p>Participants expressed a strong sense of commitment and fulfillment in teaching, supported by manageable work conditions, resilience, and positive student engagement.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 7)</p>	Connecting-discordance
Relationship of occupational stress to the psychological well-being	<p>The study revealed that occupational stress has a strong negative relationship to the psychological well-being among the respondents. This means that as the</p>	<p>Participants shared that stress causes emotional strain, affects personal life, lowers motivation and job satisfaction, reduces enjoyment in teaching, triggers</p>	Connecting-confirmation

	occupational stress of the teachers decreases, their psychological well-being increases. (Refer to Table 4)	mental distress from deadlines, and hinders professional growth. (Refer to Table 8)	
Relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention	The study revealed a significant negative strong relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention among the respondents. It means that as the level of psychological well-being decreases, their level of turnover intentions significantly increases. (Refer to table 4)	Participants noted that stress became more manageable over time, with improved emotional resilience and mental framing. Experience increased their stress tolerance, and initial challenges did not lead to long-term resignation plans. (Refer to Table 8)	Connecting-confirmation
Relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions	The study revealed that the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions is positive and strong. It means that as the level of occupational stress increases, the level of turnover intentions also increases. (Refer to table 4)	Participants shared that high workload and administrative pressure often led to burnout. As stress accumulated, many felt the job became unsustainable, triggering thoughts of career change or resignation. Persistent situational challenges weakened their commitment, leaving some with no choice but to quit. (Refer to Table 8)	Connecting-confirmation
Mediating Effect of Psychological well-being on the Relationship between Occupational Stress and Turnover Intention	In the final analysis of the mediating effect, it was revealed that psychological well-being partially mediates the relationship between occupational stress and turnover	Participants emphasized that feeling supported and valued helped buffer the effects of stress. Strong psychological well-being enabled resilience, while poor mental health intensified even minor	Connecting-confirmation

	<p>intentions among the respondents.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 5 and Figure 5)</p>	<p>stressors. They viewed well-being as essential to teaching, noting that psychological depletion often led to burnout and a higher likelihood of quitting.</p> <p>(Refer to Table 9)</p>	
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DISCUSSION

Presented in this chapter are the findings previously discussed in Chapter 3. It explores the implications of each finding by comparing it with related literature and studies, highlighting similarities and differences. The chapter also examines the quantitative data from the surveys and the key themes from the qualitative data gathered through IDS and FGD.

Status of Occupational Stress among ESL Teachers

The moderate status of occupational stress among ESL teachers shows that it is sometimes manifested. This suggests that while ESL teachers are able to manage workplace relationships effectively, their stress often stems from external factors such as students’ home environments, parental involvement, workload, and self-imposed expectations. Consequently, the challenge of balancing school and home responsibilities can significantly affect their well-being and teaching effectiveness.

The result of the current study supports the study of Balachandran et al. (2025), who revealed a moderate level of occupational stress among University teachers from Northern Kerala. It was observed that teachers were having major stressors such as too much work, lack of preparation time, and administrative (paper) work. Moreover, there were issues of progress in job, recognition, promotion, and professional development opportunities. The recent study also corroborates the study of Eres (2011), which claimed that the level of occupational stress among Macedonian teachers is moderate, it showed that the stress level of the respondent is sometimes manifested, their stress mainly comes from external factors such as threats for losing their job, workload, and self-imposed expectations. Additionally, the present study is in line with the study of Johannsen (2011) who reported that participants experienced a moderate level of occupational stress. While the current study seems to negate the findings of Wickramasinghe et al. (2022), who revealed a high level of occupational stress among secondary school teachers in Colombo, Sri Lanka.

According to Sutarto and Izzah (2022), occupational stress is a pervasive phenomenon in the modern workplace and encompasses the multifaceted interplay between job-related demands and an individual's capacity to effectively manage these

demands. It manifests as adverse physical and emotional reactions when job requirements surpass a worker's capabilities and resources. However, their prior experiences in this field help them navigate these demands effectively, keeping stress levels from becoming too high.

The Status of Psychological Well-being of ESL Teachers

The study revealed that the psychological well-being of the ESL teachers in the Philippines, was rated as high, which means that the psychological well-being of teachers is oftentimes exhibited. This suggests that ESL teachers generally feel confident in expressing their opinions, managing life responsibilities, cultivating meaningful relationships, and pursuing personal development and purpose. This implies that while ESL teachers are psychologically resilient and well-adjusted, targeted support in areas like self-reflection, recognition, and professional affirmation could further enhance their well-being and sustain their effectiveness in the classroom.

The high rating of the psychological well-being of the ESL teachers aligns with the study by Aguilar-Diaz (2023), which emphasized that teachers working in schools with strong collegial leadership, confidence in expressing themselves, fairness in discipline of life responsibilities, and mental health support systems tend to report high levels of psychological well-being. These environments foster autonomy, purpose, and emotional resilience.

In line with the findings of the current study it reverses to the research conducted by Jimenez (2021) found that teachers in Central Luzon, Philippines, generally experienced moderate psychological well-being, with occasional stress and sleep disturbances. While they maintained positive mental health, job-related pressures and resource limitations affected their overall wellness.

In addition, a study by Kurrle and Warwas (2025) conducted a systematic review of 168 studies and concluded that teacher well-being varies widely depending on individual beliefs, emotional coping strategies, and institutional support. Most studies reported moderate to high well-being, but conceptual inconsistencies make comparisons difficult

The Status of Turnover Intention of ESL Teachers

The result of this study revealed the moderate status of turnover intention among private ESL teachers in the Philippines, which means that it is sometimes observed. This suggests that teachers may not be actively seeking to leave but are open to better opportunities. This implies that school leaders must address improving work conditions, recognition, and development opportunities, structural and emotional needs such as career advancement, organizational transparency, and wellness support to reduce turnover risk and foster long-term commitment. The present study affirms with the study conducted by Santiago et al. (2022), who found out that the moderate level of teacher turnover was influenced by personal and institutional factors, with the challenge of

adapting to new environments and limited access to professional training emerging as key contributors across all perspectives. Additionally, it confirms the study of Arnup and Bowles (2016) who reported that resilience acts as a protective factor, but many teachers still show moderate intention to leave due to stress and lack of support.

The moderate status of turnover intention fails to support the study conducted by Van et al. (2024) found that teachers in low socioeconomic status (SES) schools experience high emotional exhaustion, which significantly increases their intention to transfer or quit. It also rejects the study by Nugraha (2019) who found out a high level of turnover intention and with this, there is a need for schools to have a retention program to achieve a low turnover of teachers.

Significance of the Relationship of Occupational Stress and Psychological Well-being

The result shows that occupational stress has a strong negative relationship to the psychological well-being of the ESL teachers in the Philippines. The results provide enough support that the relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being is significant. Also, it means that as the occupational stress of teachers decreases, their psychological well-being increases.

The result showing a strong negative relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being among ESL teachers in the Philippines aligns closely with the theoretical foundations of this study. The Wellness Theory (Anspaugh et al., 2006) supports the idea that holistic well-being encompassing emotional, physical, and occupational dimensions is compromised when stress levels rise, leading to diminished job satisfaction and increased turnover intention. The Job Demands-Resources Model (Demerouti et al., 2001) further explains that when ESL teachers face high demands without adequate resources, their psychological well-being deteriorates, reinforcing the significance of balancing workload with support systems. Finally, Resiliency Theory (Garmezy, 1973) highlights the potential for teachers to adapt and recover from stress through coping mechanisms, suggesting that resilience-building strategies can buffer the negative effects of occupational stress. Together, these theories validate the study's findings and imply that reducing stress and enhancing support are essential to improving teacher well-being and retention.

Significance of the Relationship between Psychological well-being and turnover intentions

The results shows that psychological well-being reveals a significant negative strong relationship with turnover intentions of teachers. This results provides sufficient evidence that the relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intentions is significant. It means that as the level of psychological well-being decreases, their level of turnover intentions significantly increases.

The negative strong relationship of psychological well-being on turnover intentions of ESL teachers aligns with the study Collie (2023) conducted a study involving 426

Australian school teachers and found that psychological well-being particularly subjective vitality and relatedness with colleagues was significantly and negatively associated with turnover intentions. Teachers who felt more energized and connected were less likely to consider leaving their jobs, while factors like time pressure and autonomy-thwarting leadership increased the likelihood of turnover. Also, it affirms the study of Coşkun et al. (2022) examined the role of psychological well-being in relation to teachers' person-organization (P-O) fit and turnover intentions. Analyzing data from 507 teachers, the study found that higher psychological well-being significantly decreased both the intent to leave the profession and the intent to transfer schools. The findings highlight that when teachers feel mentally and emotionally supported within their organizational environment, they are less likely to consider leaving.

Furthermore, the result also aligns with the study of Zhang et al. (2022) investigated teacher burnout and turnover intention in higher education, revealing that job satisfaction closely tied to psychological well-being—significantly and negatively impacts turnover intention. Their findings show that teachers with higher well-being and satisfaction are less likely to leave, while burnout increases the likelihood of turnover.

Significance of the Relationship between Occupational Stress and Turnover Intentions

The relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions of the ESL teachers in Philippines is positive and strong. This suggests that as occupational stress intensifies, the likelihood of teachers considering leaving their positions also rises, confirming the substantial impact of stress on their intent to exit the profession.

The positive and strong relationship of occupational stress on turnover intentions supports the findings of Ladres and Garcia (2025), who conducted a study among public school teachers in the Philippines and found that high levels of occupational stress and burnout were significantly associated with increased turnover intent. The research identified curricular stress and negative attitudes toward students as key predictors, emphasizing that unmanaged stress directly contributes to teachers' desire to leave the profession. Moreover, it also corroborates with the study of Karimi et al. (2025) which investigated occupational stress among L2 teachers and found that elevated stress levels directly predicted higher turnover intentions. Using structural equation modeling, the study revealed that psychological well-being mediated this relationship, confirming that as stress increases, teachers' desire to leave intensifies. The findings emphasize the emotional toll of teaching and the need for supportive interventions to reduce attrition. Thus, the presence of occupational stress plays a critical role in influencing teachers' turnover intentions. When stress levels are high due to excessive workload, lack of support, or emotional strain teachers are more likely to consider leaving their positions. To address this, schools must implement proactive strategies such as promoting mental health awareness, ensuring manageable workloads, offering emotional and professional support, and fostering a culture of care and responsiveness. Reducing occupational stress is essential for retaining teachers and sustaining a healthy, committed workforce.

Mediating Effect of Psychological Well-being on the Relationship between Occupational Stress and Turnover Intentions

The study's findings reveal that psychological well-being partially mediates the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. This interprets that psychological well-being serves as a key mechanism through which occupational stress affects teachers' intention to leave their jobs. This underscores the importance of viewing psychological well-being not just as an outcome, but as a mediating factor that shapes how stress translates into turnover intentions.

The research findings confirm the previous studies by Karimi et al. (2025), who conducted a study among 353 Iranian L2 teachers and found that psychological well-being significantly mediated the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. Using structural equation modeling, the study revealed that while occupational stress directly influenced turnover intention, psychological well-being served as a partial mediator, reducing the strength of this relationship. This suggests that enhancing teachers' psychological well-being can buffer the negative effects of stress and lower the likelihood of turnover.

Standpoints of the Participants on the Salient Points of the

The standpoints of the participants on the salient points of the quantitative results provide valuable insights and enrich the understanding of the findings. By examining the perspectives of the participants, this section delves deeper into how occupational stress, Psychological well-being, and turnover intention are perceived and experienced in practice. Participant viewpoints offer a nuanced interpretation of the data, highlighting practical implications, contextual factors, and the lived realities of ESL teachers in the Philippines. These perspectives bridge the gap between statistical outcomes and lived experiences. This part discusses the confirmation status of the overall mean of each variable and the significant influence between the variables.

Confirmed Moderate Status on Occupational stress of Teachers. The participants confirm the moderate status of the occupational stress of ESL teachers as acquired in the quantitative results of the study. The qualitative findings of the study corroborate the quantitative results, confirming a moderate status of occupational stress among teachers, primarily driven by time constraints and dual teaching responsibilities, which contribute to fatigue. However, this stress is mitigated by teachers' strong passion and professional commitment, as well as their ability to adapt to student-related challenges and occasional technical issues. Over time, stress tends to decrease through accumulated experience and improved emotional regulation. Positive interactions with students further serve as a buffer, reinforcing resilience and sustaining motivation despite the demands of the role.

The findings align well that stress is buffered by professional commitment and adapts over time in the study conducted by Antoniou et al. (2023) explored occupational stress among mainstream and special needs primary school teachers, finding that while stress levels were present particularly due to time pressure, administrative challenges,

and student behavior they were not uniformly severe. Teachers demonstrated resilience and self-efficacy, which helped moderate the impact of stress. Moreover, the findings align with Ellovido and Quirap (2024) revealed that while educators experience moderate stress particularly from subject-related and working conditions they also demonstrate effective coping mechanisms.

Confirmed high level of psychological well-being. The qualitative analysis confirmed a high level of psychological well-being. Largely driven by appreciation from students and parents, which fosters emotional fulfillment and reinforces their sense of purpose. Witnessing student growth and engaging positively with learners energizes teachers, strengthens career satisfaction, and motivates ongoing professional development. Supportive and open learning environments further cultivate a positive mindset, suggesting that school administrators should continue nurturing these conditions to sustain teacher morale and enhance overall educational outcomes. This underscores the importance of recognizing teacher contributions and maintaining strong, affirming relationships within the school community. The ESL teachers in the Philippines revealed that appreciation from students and parents enhances emotional fulfillment. This is congruent with the statement of Pedditzi et al. (2021), who revealed that teacher-parent and teacher-student satisfaction were significant predictors of personal accomplishment, a key component of emotional fulfillment. This underscores the importance of appreciation and positive interactions in sustaining teachers' emotional health.

Moreover, the qualitative analysis also found that witnessing student growth creates deep professional purpose. It supports the research of Muir et al. (2021) who found that when teachers engaged in learning based on student data, they experienced a stronger sense of professional fulfillment and motivation. This connection between student improvement and teacher purpose highlights the emotional and professional rewards educators gain from seeing their efforts translate into student success. Also, positive student engagement energizes and motivates teachers (Robinson, 2022). Thus, when teachers perceive students as engaged and responsive, it reinforces their sense of purpose and invigorates their teaching practices, contributing to overall well-being and professional satisfaction.

Disconfirmed moderate level of turnover intention. The qualitative analysis disconfirmed the quantitative results of a moderate level of turnover intention. The ESL teachers in the Philippines revealed that most educators demonstrate a strong sense of commitment and professional growth. Their personal fulfillment, sense of calling, and satisfaction with work conditions contribute to their decision to remain in the profession. Despite occasional technical or environmental challenges, teachers show resilience and continue to find motivation through positive relationships with students and meaningful engagement in the classroom. The disconfirmed moderate level of turnover intention, aligns the study of Grillo and Kier (2021) explored why teachers remain in high-need school contexts. They found that strong professional identities, social justice motivations, and supportive relationships with students and colleagues foster long-term commitment and resilience.

Additionally, a strong sense of commitment and professional growth disconfirmed a moderate level of turnover intention. A study by Collie (2023), who found that job resources such as autonomy-supportive leadership and strong relationships with colleagues and students were positively associated with teacher well-being and professional growth, and negatively associated with turnover intentions. Also, it supports the study of Farahmandpour, and Voelkel (2025), which found that professional development, leadership quality, and school-level support significantly reduce turnover intention and promote teacher retention and growth. Similarly, the idea of Yang and Chan (2025), who identified organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and psychological resilience as key predictors of low turnover intention. It emphasized the growing importance of professional identity and personal fulfillment in teacher retention.

Likewise, the result showed that acceptable work conditions and schedules disconfirmed the quantitative result. This support the statement of Ertürk (2022) which showed that teachers with moderate-to-high perceptions of work quality including career satisfaction, work-life balance, and acceptable working conditions exhibited lower turnover intentions.

Standpoints of the Participants on the Relationships between Occupational Stress, Psychological Well-being and Turnover Intention

In this study, participants shared their insights on the relationships between occupational stress, psychological well-being and turnover among ESL teachers. Their views were analyzed and revealed essential themes, such as confirmed strong negative relationship between occupational stress and Psychological Well-being; disconfirmed significant negative strong relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention; confirmed positive and strong relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions; and confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-being to the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions of ESL teachers.

Confirmed strong negative relationship of occupational stress to the psychological well-being among ESL Teachers. The quantitative results of this study show that occupational stress has a strong negative relationship to the psychological well-being of teachers. The results provides enough support that the relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being is significant. Also, it means that as occupational stress of teachers decreases their psychological well-being increases. From the IDI and FGD, a confirmed strong negative relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being was revealed. It leads to emotional strain and anxiety, often spilling over into personal life and affecting overall mental health. This persistent stress diminishes motivation and job satisfaction, making it harder for teachers to find joy in their daily teaching moments. The high pressure from deadlines and reporting requirements further intensifies mental distress, while ongoing stress also hinders professional growth and the capacity for continuous learning. The result corroborates the idea of Andres (2024), who reported that stress leads to emotional exhaustion, diminished motivation, and impaired well-being.

Confirmed significant negative strong relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention. The quantitative results of this study show the confirmation of a strong negative relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention. It suggests that, teachers with higher emotional resilience and mental framing are less likely to consider leaving their jobs. As stress becomes more manageable over time and tolerance improves with experience, the work environment feels less overwhelming, reducing the risk of resignation. Practically, this highlights the importance of investing in teacher wellness programs, mentorship, and coping skill development to strengthen psychological well-being and promote long-term retention. This finding aligns with Nazari and Oghyanous (2021), which found that while psychological well-being and occupational stress were related to turnover intention, the strength of these relationships weakened with teaching experience. Experienced teachers demonstrated greater emotional resilience and stress tolerance, and their psychological well-being had a reduced impact on their intent to leave. This supports the idea that stress becomes more manageable over time, and initial psychological strain does not necessarily lead to long-term resignation plans.

Confirmed positive and strong relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. The relationship between occupational stress and turnover intention is strongly affirmed, as persistent stressors significantly undermine teachers' commitment to their profession. The qualitative findings reinforce the quantitative evidence, revealing that high workloads, administrative pressure, and emotional exhaustion intensify the desire for career change. Participants consistently reported that accumulated personal and professional stress made their roles unsustainable, with many expressing that ongoing difficulties and situational stressors left them with no viable option but to resign. This finding aligns with Collie (2023) which found that job demands such as time pressure, disruptive student behavior, and autonomy-thwarting leadership were positively associated with turnover intentions. Teachers experiencing high levels of stress reported weakened professional commitment and a stronger desire to leave the profession. The findings confirm that excessive and persistent stress makes the job unsustainable, aligning with the conclusion that stress often leaves teachers with no other option but to quit.

Confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-being to the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions

This section discusses the participants' standpoints on the partial mediating effect of the mediating variable (psychological well-being) on the relationship between the independent variable (occupational stress) and the dependent variable (turnover intention).

Confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-being in the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions. The qualitative findings strongly support the quantitative results by illustrating how psychological well-being partially mediate the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions among ESL teachers. Participants reported that while stress directly affects teachers' intent to leave, strong

mental health can buffer its impact. When teachers feel supported and valued, they're more resilient; when depleted, even small stressors can lead to burnout and resignation. This highlights the need for school leaders to prioritize mental health as a strategic resource for retention and staff well-being. This finding aligns with the statement that psychological well-being performs a mediatory role between occupational stress and turnover intention, the ability to maintain well-being and respond resiliently to professional challenges is recognized as a valuable capacity for teachers (Karimi et al., 2025).

Data Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

This section presents the integration of quantitative and qualitative findings. Hands (2022) emphasizes that data integration in mixed methods research is a critical step for achieving a comprehensive understanding of complex phenomena. By systematically merging qualitative and quantitative data particularly during the interpretation phase researchers can uncover deeper insights and enhance the credibility of their conclusions. Hands illustrates this process through convergence tables, highlighting how integrated analysis strengthens the explanatory power of mixed methods designs.

Connecting-Confirmation for the Status of Occupational Stress, Psychological well-being, and Turnover Intention of Teachers. The data integration process in this study employed a connecting-confirmation approach, seamlessly aligning quantitative results with qualitative insights to provide a comprehensive understanding of occupational stress, psychological well-being, and turnover Intention among ESL teachers in the Philippines.

On the moderate status of occupational stress among ESL teachers, the integration of quantitative and qualitative results demonstrates a coherent understanding of the issue. The quantitative finding corroborates the qualitative feedback where teachers articulated their experiences and challenges, confirming the sometimes-experienced stress levels. This is congruent with the findings of Antonio et al. (2023), who confirm that personal and contextual factors influence stress perception and coping. They feel overwhelmed by the continuous demand to manage dual teaching loads and technical issues into their teaching practices, exacerbating their stress levels. Additionally, the result is in agreement with the view of Labrado (2022) that the findings confirm that intrinsic motivation buffers occupational stress. As noted by Andres (2024), the qualitative data confirmed and contextualised the moderate stress levels found quantitatively.

Further, the integration between quantitative and qualitative results on the high status of psychological well-being among ESL teachers shows a strong alignment. The quantitative data indicates a high status. This is confirmed qualitatively through interviews and focus group discussions, where teachers express that appreciation and student growth enhance emotional fulfilment and purpose, also, positive engagement and progress bring joy, motivation, and inspire continued professional growth. The result aligns with Aziku & Zhang (2024) who reported moderate to high psychological well-being among teachers. Qualitative feedback revealed that appreciation, student progress, and supportive school climates boosted emotional resilience and fulfilment, reinforcing and

deepening the survey results. According to Kurrle & Warwas (2025), identified that high psychological well-being among teachers was quantitatively linked to emotional engagement and professional growth, while qualitative accounts highlighted joy and motivation driven by student development and recognition. A synthesis of multiple studies confirmed that emotional fulfillment and a strong sense of purpose aligned with and deepened the statistical trends. Additionally, this supports the view of Arvidsson et al. (2019) that teachers with high psychological well-being showed lower burnout and greater self-efficacy, according to quantitative data. Qualitative accounts revealed that emotional satisfaction from student success and appreciation helped buffer stress and sustain motivation, reinforcing the protective role of well-being highlighted in the statistics.

Furthermore, the quantitative results show a moderate status of turnover intention among ESL teachers, indicating that the intention to leave is oftentimes practiced. These quantitative data are seamlessly a connecting-discordance by qualitative insights from IDIs and FGD, where teachers reported high levels of commitment and fulfillment, driven by manageable workloads, emotional resilience, and meaningful engagement with students. This connecting-discordance highlights a nuanced reality while statistical data points to moderate turnover risk, the lived experiences of teachers suggest strong intrinsic motivation and satisfaction. The implication is that retention strategies should focus not only on reducing stressors but also on reinforcing the positive emotional and relational aspects of teaching that sustain commitment.

Connecting-Confirmation for the Relationships among Occupational stress, Psychological well-being, and Turnover Intentions of the ESL Teachers. The data integration process in this study utilized a connecting-confirmation approach, effectively aligning qualitative findings with quantitative results to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between occupational stress, psychological well-being, and turnover intentions among ESL teachers.

The connecting-confirmation integration of quantitative and qualitative results reveals that occupational stress has a strong negative relationship to the psychological well-being among the respondents. Quantitatively, the results provides enough support that the relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being is significant. Also, it means that as the occupational stress of teachers decreases, their psychological well-being increases. Qualitatively, the findings are confirmed through IDIs and FGD, where participants shared that stress drains motivation, disrupts personal life, reduces job satisfaction, and hinders growth, emphasizing the need for support systems to protect educators' well-being. This integration underscores the critical impact of occupational stress on teachers' mental health and professional fulfillment. It highlights the urgent need for systemic interventions such as wellness programs, workload management, and emotional support to safeguard educators' psychological well-being and sustain their effectiveness in the classroom.

Meanwhile, the quantitative findings from the study through a connecting-confirmation nature of integration, revealed a significant negative strong relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention among the respondents. The

study confirms that lower psychological well-being increases turnover intention. Teachers noted that stress became manageable over time, with experience building resilience. Early challenges didn't lead to resignation, highlighting the need for wellness support to retain staff. Qualitatively, this correlation is confirmed by participants; the qualitative insights from the teachers introduce a connecting confirmation: despite experiencing stress, many respondents developed emotional resilience and mental reframing strategies over time. Their accumulated experience helped them manage stress more effectively, reducing the likelihood of actual turnover even when psychological well-being was temporarily compromised.

Lastly, the study's quantitative analysis indicates that the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions is positive and strong among ESL teachers, implying that as stress levels rise, so does the likelihood that individuals will consider leaving their jobs. Qualitatively, this finding is confirmed by participants, who described how high workloads, administrative burdens, and persistent pressure led to burnout, emotional exhaustion, and ultimately, thoughts of resignation. The "connecting-confirmation" theme indicates that both data strands, statistical and narrative, are aligned. Participants' lived experiences validate the numerical trend: occupational stress is not just a theoretical predictor of turnover, it's a lived reality that actively shapes career decisions. The result is in agreement with the view of Ladres and Garcia (2025) found a significant positive relationship between occupational stress and turnover intent among teachers. Curricular stress and burnout were major predictors of resignation plans. Also, this supports the findings of Karimi (2025) that occupational stress directly predicted turnover intentions among L2 teachers. Psychological well-being and grit acted as mediators, but the core relationship remained strong.

Connecting-Confirmation for the psychological well-being partially mediates the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions among the respondents. The quantitative results of the study indicate a significant partial mediating effect of psychological well-being on the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions among teachers, demonstrating that while occupational stress directly influences turnover intentions, psychological well-being acts as a buffer reducing the intensity of that relationship. Qualitatively, this relationship is corroborated by participants who shared that feeling supported, valued, and emotionally resilient helped them manage stress more effectively. They viewed psychological well-being not just as a personal asset, but as a professional necessity essential for sustaining commitment and avoiding burnout. This result underscores a vital insight: stress may be inevitable, but its consequences are not. By strengthening psychological well-being, institutions can transform stress from a resignation trigger into a manageable challenge.

Implications for Educational Practices

The moderate level of occupational stress among teachers, shaped by manageable student-related challenges, time demands, and occasional technical issues, highlights the importance of adaptive strategies in educational practice. Teachers' passion, professional commitment, and emotional resilience help buffer stress, while

positive student engagement further offsets fatigue. This suggests that schools should prioritize professional development focused on stress management, foster supportive environments, and promote meaningful teacher-student relationships to sustain well-being and performance.

Further, the confirmed high level of psychological well-being among teachers highlights the importance of fostering emotionally supportive educational environments. Appreciation from students and parents, along with visible student progress, reinforces teachers' sense of purpose, motivation, and career satisfaction. Educational practices should therefore prioritize cultivating open, respectful, and engaging classrooms, encouraging regular feedback and recognition, and promoting professional growth through meaningful student-teacher interactions. These elements not only sustain teacher well-being but also enhance instructional quality and long-term retention.

In addition, the disconfirmed moderate level of turnover intention suggests that teachers are largely committed to their roles, driven by personal fulfillment, professional growth, and a strong sense of calling. Educational practices should therefore focus on sustaining this commitment by maintaining acceptable work conditions, fostering positive student-teacher relationships, and supporting resilience through responsive leadership and stable infrastructure. By nurturing passion and reinforcing the meaningful impact of teaching, schools can further reduce turnover risks and promote long-term educator engagement.

Meanwhile, the confirmed strong negative relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being underscores the urgent need for educational practices that actively reduce stressors and promote mental health. Schools should implement supportive measures such as manageable workloads, realistic deadlines, and streamlined reporting systems to prevent emotional strain and burnout. Creating a culture of care through wellness programs, peer support, and open communication can help restore motivation, job satisfaction, and enjoyment in teaching. Prioritizing teacher well-being is essential not only for personal fulfillment but also for sustaining professional growth and high-quality education.

Likewise, the confirmed strong negative relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention suggests that while psychological strain may occur, it does not necessarily lead to resignation, especially as teachers develop emotional resilience and stress tolerance over time. Educational practices should therefore focus on fostering long-term coping skills, promoting mental framing strategies, and creating environments that support gradual adaptation. By emphasizing professional growth, peer support, and reflective practice, schools can help educators navigate early stress without compromising retention, reinforcing the idea that initial challenges are not predictors of long-term turnover.

Moreover, the confirmed strong positive relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions highlights the urgent need for educational practices that actively reduce chronic stressors and promote teacher retention. Schools should prioritize

workload management, streamline administrative demands, and provide consistent emotional and professional support to prevent burnout. Creating responsive systems that address situational challenges and foster open communication can help sustain commitment and job satisfaction. By investing in teacher well-being and building resilient work environments, educational institutions can mitigate turnover risks and preserve instructional quality.

Subsequently, the confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-being in the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions highlights its pivotal role in shaping teachers' reactions to workplace challenges. Educational practices should therefore prioritize fostering a supportive and appreciative environment that strengthens psychological well-being, enabling teachers to build resilience against stress. By promoting mental health resources, encouraging open communication, and recognizing teachers' contributions, schools can buffer the impact of stress and reduce the likelihood of burnout and resignation, ultimately sustaining a committed and thriving teaching workforce. The implication is that psychological well-being serves as a key protective factor against the negative effects of occupational stress on turnover intention. Schools that actively support teachers' mental health through recognition, open communication, and wellness initiatives can reduce burnout and foster long-term commitment, helping to build a resilient and stable teaching workforce.

Conclusions

This chapter discusses conclusions and recommendations for practical applications and future research. It synthesizes the critical relationships identified between occupational stress, psychological well-being, and turnover intentions, with significant implications for improving educational practices and outcomes.

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

ESL teachers experience a moderate status of occupational stress, suggesting that while challenges such as time management, dual teaching loads, and occasional technical issues do contribute to fatigue, they are largely manageable through adaptation, experience, and emotional regulation. Teachers demonstrate resilience, drawing strength from their passion for the profession and their commitment to student success. Positive student engagement and appreciation serve as powerful buffers, reinforcing motivation and mitigating the emotional toll of daily demands. Over time, educators develop coping strategies that transform stress into a manageable aspect of their professional journey rather than a debilitating force. This conclusion highlights the importance of fostering supportive environments that nurture teacher adaptability, reinforce their sense of purpose, and sustain their psychological well-being amid the evolving demands of the educational landscape.

ESL teachers demonstrate a high level of psychological well-being, reflecting a deeply rooted sense of fulfillment, purpose, and motivation that stems from meaningful interactions within the educational environment. Appreciation from students and parents

fosters emotional satisfaction, while witnessing student growth reinforces a profound professional identity and joy in teaching. Positive engagement and progress in the classroom not only energize educators but also strengthen their commitment to continuous development and instructional excellence. Supportive and open learning spaces further cultivate a climate of positivity, allowing teachers to thrive both personally and professionally. This conclusion underscores the vital role of relational and environmental factors in sustaining teacher well-being, which in turn enhances educational quality and long-term retention.

The disconfirmed moderate level of turnover intention among teachers indicates a prevailing sense of dedication and stability within the profession, driven by deep personal fulfillment, a strong sense of calling, and opportunities for continuous professional growth. Despite facing technical or environmental challenges, educators demonstrate resilience and adaptability, supported by acceptable work conditions and schedules that help sustain their engagement. Positive relationships with students and the joy derived from teaching further reinforce their commitment, making resignation a less likely outcome. This conclusion highlights the importance of nurturing these intrinsic and extrinsic motivators within educational environments to maintain teacher retention and foster a thriving, passionate workforce.

The confirmed strong negative relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being underscores the profound impact that persistent work-related pressures have on teachers' emotional and professional lives. As stress intensifies—driven by deadlines, administrative demands, and workload—it not only triggers anxiety and emotional strain but also spills over into personal domains, eroding motivation, job satisfaction, and the ability to find joy in teaching. This chronic tension compromises teachers' capacity for professional growth and learning, creating a cycle that threatens both their well-being and effectiveness in the classroom. The findings highlight the urgent need for educational systems to prioritize stress reduction strategies, cultivate supportive work environments, and implement policies that safeguard teachers' mental health to ensure sustainable engagement and high-quality education.

The confirmed strong negative relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention suggests that teachers with higher emotional resilience and mental framing are less likely to consider leaving their jobs. As stress becomes more manageable over time and experience builds tolerance, initial challenges do not necessarily lead to resignation. This highlights the practical need for schools to invest in long-term wellness strategies, mentoring, and emotional support systems that help teachers develop coping skills and sustain their commitment despite early stressors. Meanwhile, the confirmed strong positive relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions reveals a critical challenge in the teaching profession, where escalating workloads, administrative burdens, and persistent situational stressors contribute directly to burnout and a growing desire to leave the job. As stress accumulates both personally and professionally—it erodes teachers' sense of commitment and makes the work environment feel increasingly unsustainable. This pattern underscores the urgent need for educational institutions to address systemic stress factors, implement

supportive policies, and create conditions that promote teacher well-being, in order to prevent attrition and preserve the stability and quality of the educational workforce.

Psychological well-being partially mediates in the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions, highlighting its essential role in shaping how teachers respond to workplace challenges. While stress directly influences the desire to leave, psychological well-being serves as a protective factor that enhances resilience and reduces the likelihood of burnout and resignation. Teachers who feel supported and valued are better equipped to manage stress, whereas those with poor mental health are more vulnerable to its effects, even from minor stressors. This finding underscores the importance of fostering psychological well-being within educational environments, positioning it not only as a personal asset but as a strategic resource for sustaining teacher engagement, reducing turnover, and promoting a healthier, more stable workforce.

The participants confirmed the moderate rating for teachers' occupational stress found in the quantitative results of the study. The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings confirms that occupational stress among teachers is moderate and often manageable, shaped by both external demands and internal coping mechanisms. While time constraints and dual teaching loads contribute to fatigue, teachers demonstrate resilience through adaptation, professional commitment, and emotional regulation. Technical challenges are infrequent, and the positive impact of student engagement provides a meaningful counterbalance to stress. Over time, experience and a sense of purpose help educators navigate pressures more effectively, suggesting that while stress is present, it does not dominate the professional experience. This conclusion emphasizes the importance of fostering supportive environments that reinforce teachers' capacity to adapt and thrive.

The high overall mean of psychological well-being among teachers, supported by both quantitative and qualitative findings, confirms that ESL teachers frequently experience emotional fulfillment, motivation, and a strong sense of purpose. Appreciation from students and parents, along with visible student progress, reinforces their joy in teaching and inspires ongoing professional growth, highlighting the positive impact of supportive relationships and meaningful engagement in sustaining teacher well-being.

The moderate level of turnover intention among teachers, as reflected in the overall mean, suggests that while thoughts of leaving the profession are occasionally present, they are often outweighed by a strong sense of commitment, personal fulfillment, and resilience. Qualitative insights reveal that manageable work conditions and meaningful student relationships play a crucial role in sustaining motivation and reducing the likelihood of resignation, indicating that supportive environments and positive engagement can effectively counterbalance turnover risks.

The confirmed strong negative relationship between occupational stress and psychological well-being indicates that as teachers experience higher levels of stress, their emotional health, motivation, and overall job satisfaction significantly decline.

Qualitative responses reinforce this by revealing how stress spills into personal life, diminishes enjoyment in teaching, and obstructs professional growth. This conclusion highlights the urgent need for educational environments to actively reduce stressors and promote mental wellness to preserve teachers' psychological well-being and sustain their effectiveness in the classroom.

Additionally, the study confirmed a strong negative relationship between psychological well-being and turnover intention, indicating that lower well-being significantly increases the likelihood of teachers considering resignation. However, qualitative insights revealed a discordance, as many participants developed emotional resilience and stress tolerance over time, allowing them to manage challenges without pursuing resignation. This suggests that while psychological well-being is a key factor in turnover intention, experience and adaptive coping strategies can mitigate its impact, highlighting the importance of fostering long-term resilience and professional growth in educational settings.

The confirmed strong positive relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions indicates that increasing stress levels significantly heighten the likelihood of teachers considering resignation. As workloads and administrative pressures intensify, burnout becomes more prevalent, making the job feel unsustainable and weakening professional commitment. Participants' experiences reveal that persistent stress not only affects their well-being but also drives serious contemplation of career change, emphasizing the urgent need for educational systems to address stressors to retain a stable and motivated teaching workforce.

The confirmed partial mediation of psychological well-being in the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intentions highlights its crucial role in shaping how teachers cope with stress and make career decisions. While stress directly influences turnover intentions, strong psychological well-being helps buffer its impact by fostering resilience and emotional stability. Participants emphasized that feeling supported and valued enhances well-being, whereas poor mental health magnifies stress and increases the risk of burnout and resignation. This finding underscores the importance of promoting psychological well-being in educational settings to reduce turnover and support teacher retention.

The confirmation of the quantitative findings by qualitative results during the integration of the results provided concrete evidence of essential themes that emerged in both phases. This integration of results also offered a comprehensive understanding of the teachers' turnover intentions and key themes. The identified themes helped to enhance and clarify the depth of the variables under study, as well as the mediating role of psychological well-being on the relationship between occupational stress and turnover intention among ESL teachers.

Recommendations

In the light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for consideration by school administrators and education policymakers:

1. In reducing occupational stress, ESL company administrators may develop comprehensive systems of support that would improve professional development and well-being, increase collaborative practices, and further promote work-life balance to reduce occupational stress among teachers;
2. To reduce turnover intention, ESL Company should maintain manageable workloads, foster positive student relationships, and support teachers' professional growth and resilience to strengthen commitment and job satisfaction;
3. To maintain high psychological well-being, ESL Company should continue recognizing teachers' efforts, encouraging student engagement, and supporting professional growth in a positive learning environment.
4. To support ESL teachers in managing occupational stress and enhancing psychological well-being, school administrators may implement targeted in-service training programs such as stress management workshops, time and workload balancing seminars, and resilience-building sessions; and
5. To advance research, academic company may explore how occupational stress, psychological well-being, and turnover intention interact among ESL teachers, considering demographic and contextual factors to guide more targeted interventions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure strict adherence to ethical standards, the researcher upheld the ethical standards in research by submitting the study for review and approval by the UIC-REC. The researcher also took necessary precautions to comply with ethical procedures during participant interactions, addressed study-related concerns, and maintained the anonymity of research findings. Since the topic related to the researcher's line of work and area of interest as an educator, particularly at her center, she was inspired to carry out the study. Since 2019, the researcher had worked as an ESL teacher. She acknowledged her limited exposure to mixed methods research. With this, she sought advice and direction from peers skilled in this approach, her dissertation adviser, and knowledgeable panelists. In order to improve the study, the researcher was conscientious and receptive of the advice from her adviser, Dr. Avee Joy B. Dayaganon, who held a Ph.D. in Educational Leadership, served as the Vice-President for Academics at the University of the Immaculate Conception, and was a seasoned PAASCU Accreditor and CHED RQAT member in Region XI. Alongside guidance from a technical panel, ethics committee, and peers proficient in mixed methods research, the researcher ensured the proper implementation of the study's methodology and the successful completion of the academic endeavor. Additionally, the researcher received training in this area of expertise and passed the comprehensive exam. To conclude, she pursued the study because of

the prevailing issues regarding ESL teachers' turnover intention in the Philippines and was assured of her adviser's readiness to assist her toward its completion.

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